

TA'LIM TASHKILOTLARIDA TASVIRIY FAOLIYAT MASHG'ULOTLARINI TASHKIL ETISH

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida bolalar ijodkorligini rivojlantirishda tasviriy faoliyat mashg'ulotlarini tashkil etish texnologiyalari bayon etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Ijodkorlik, tasviriy faoliyat, san'at markazi, ta'limiy rasm.

ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯ КУРСОВ ИЗОБРАЖИТЕЛЬНОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ В ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯХ

Аннотация. В данной статье описаны технологии организации изобразительной деятельности по развитию творчества детей в дошкольных образовательных организациях.

Ключевые слова: Креативность, визуальная активность, арт – центр образовательная картинка.

ORGANIZING PICTURE ACTIVITY COURSES IN EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

Abstract. This article describes the technologies of organizing visual activities for the development of children's creativity in preschool educational institutions.

Key words: Creativity, visual activity, art center, educational picture.

Prezidentimiz Shavkat Mirziyoyevning O'zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyasi qabulqilinganining 25 yilligiga bag'ishlangan tantanali marosimdagi ma'ruzarida "Maktabgachata'lim sohasida ana shunday ulkan islohotlarni hayotga joriy etish biz uchun hamqarz, hamfarzdir. Qanchalik qiyin bo'lmasin, bu tarixiy vazifani amalga oshirishimiz shart vaunibarchamiz birgalikda albatta bajaramiz". Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotida tasviriyfaoliyatmashg'ulotlarini rejalashtirish va hisobga olish zarur. Tasviriy faoliyat – bu bolalarni o'zoldigaqo'ygan maqsadlarini bajarishda tinmay mehnat qilishga undovchi faoliyatdir. Tasviriyfaoliyatbolalarga estetik tarbiya berishning asosiy vositasi hisoblanadi. Har bir predmetningkatta-kichikligini, rangini, shaklini, fazoda joylashishini ajratish bu estetik sezginingbo'laklarihisoblanadi. Bolalarda estetik sezgining rivojlanishi – rangi, ritmi, proporsiyani chuqurroqsezishbilan bog'liqdir Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotida tasviriy faoliyat bo'yichaishlarnirejalashtirishda asosiy tamoyili, bu tasviriy faoliyatni ta'lim-tarbiyaviy ishningengmuhimbo'limlaridan biri sifatida qarash hisoblanadi.

Tasviriy faoliyat bo'yicha ishni ma'lumbir vaqtgarejalashtirishda, shu davrda faoliyatning boshqa turlari bo'yicha amalga oshiriladiganta'limtarbiyaviy ishlarni ham nazarda tutmoq lozim. Tasviriy faoliyat bo'yicha mashg'ulotlarnirejalashtirishda, albatta tasviriy faoliyat mashg'ulotlari o'rtasida o'zaro bog'liqlikni hamhisobgaolmoq zarurdir. Tasviriy faoliyatning har bir turi o'ziga xos vazifalarni hal etadi, ammoqandaybo'lsa-da, ularni bir yo'nalish, maqsad bo'yicha (tevarakatrof, hayotning xilma-xil, o'zigaxosko'rinishlardagi tasviri) birlashadilar. Tasviriy faoliyat bo'yicha ishni rejalashtirishdatarbiyachi, albatta har bir turdagi mashg'ulotlar soniga qat'iy rioya qilishi lozim. Tasviriy faoliyat bo'yichamashg'ulotlarni rejalashtirish, yuqoridagilardan tashqari,

mashg'ulot qanday materiallarbilano'tkazilsa, maqsadga muvofiq bo'lishini ham tarbiyachi nazarda tutmog'i lozim. Tasviriyfaoliyat mashg'ulotlari – bu rasm chizish, loy, applikasiya, qurishyasash mashg'ulotlaridir.

Bumashg'ulotlar maktabgacha ta'lim muassasasining barcha guruhlarida aniq bir vaqtda, kuntartibiasosida uyushtiriladi. Hamma mashg'ulotlar uch qismga bo'linadi: – mashg'ulotningboshlanishi–topshiriqni tushuntirish; – mashg'ulotning borishi–topshiriqni bolalar tomonidanbajarilishi; – mashg'ulotning yakuni–bolalar bilan bajarilgan topshiriqni tahlil qilish.Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti rasm faoliyatini san'at markazlarida rejalashtiriladi. San'atmarkazi:Ta'limiy rasm chizish. Rasm: Kamalak va yomg'ir. Maqsad: Turlitasviriy vositalar orqali tabiat haqidagi tasavvurlarini mustaqil va ijodiytasvirlashgao'rgatishda davom etish. Kamalakni tasvirlashga nisbatan qiziqish uyg'otish Mashg'ulotgatayyorgarlik: Kamalakning tasviri bilan tanishtirish Kamalak to'g'risida topishmoqaytish. Kerakli jihoz va materiallar: Katta hajmdagi oq va havo rangdagi qog'oz (jamoaviy 554 albom tuzilsa bir xil hajmdagi qog'oz), akvarel bo'yog'i, turli hajmdagi mo'yqalam, suv, matova qog'oz salfetkalar, mo'yqalam uchun turgichlar.

Faoliyatning borishi:

1. Tarbiyachi bolalarga quvonch nima ekanligi to'g'risida fikr yuritishniva so'zlashishni taklif etadi.

2. Tarbiyachi «kamalak» so'zini tahlil etilishiniso'raydi (quyosh yoyi yoki quvonch yoyi, quvonchli yoy). Tarbiyachi kimhaqiqiykamalakni ko'rganligini va bu quvonchli voqea to'g'risida gapirib berishni so'raydi.

2. So'ngra tarbiyachi bolalarning kamalak haqidagi, uatmosferahodisasi sifatida, yilning iliq kunlarida osmonda ko'rish mumkinligini, mayda, iliqyomg'ir bir yoqda, bir yoqda quyoshning nurlari sochganida, quyosh orasidanyomg'irtomchilari yoqqanida kamalak hosil qilishi haqidagi tasavvurlarini aniqlaydi.

3. Tarbiyachi bolalardan kamalakning rangini bilishlarini so'raydi, vahamma vaqt ham bu ranglar aniq bir tartibda joylashishini.

4. Bolalarning intilishlaridan so'ng kamalak ranglarini joylashishtartibinieslatadi: qizil, to'qsariq, sariq, yashil, havo rang, ko'k, binafsha rang.

6. So'ngratarbiyachi molbertda yoyning boshqa yoy ustiga joylashtirishni ko'rsatadi.

Prezident Sh.Mirziyoevning O'zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyasi qabulqilinganining 25 yilligiga bag'ishlangan tantanali marosimdagi ma'ruzasidan. 07.12.2017 yil Qo'shimcha: Endi bolalar mo'yqalam, akvarelni ranglar bilan tajriba o'tkazadi, qizil rangnisariq rang bilan va sariq rangni ko'k rang bilan aralashtiradi. E'tiborgamolikjihati: Mashg'ulotdan so'ng bolalarga «Kamalak» haqidagi al'bomni jihozlashtopshiriladi.

Tasviriy faoliyatga o'rgatish metodikasi dasturi doirasidaberilayotgan mavzular maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari tarbiyachilari kasbiyqayta tayyorlash kurslari o'quv rejasi asosida shakllantirilganbo'lib, tinglovchilarda tarbiyalanuvchilarni tasviriy faoliyatga o'rgatish metodikasiga oid kasb mahoratini, o'quv-uslubiy faoliyatini yuksaltirish bilan bog'liq kompetensiyalarini rivojlantiradi.

Quyidagi tavsiyalarni beramiz:

1. Ijodiy qobiliyatni rivojlantirishda mozaika usulini qo'llashdamateriallarning xilma-xilligi (Tabiiy, tashlandiq, qogo'z) foydalanilsa:
2. Ijodiy qobiliyatni rivojlantirishda mozaika usulidan guruhishlarimetodikasidan foydalanilsa:
3. Ijodiy qobiliyatni rivojlantirishda mozaika usulidan mayda matorikalarnishakllantirish mashlaridan foydalanilsa:
4. Ijodiy qobiliyatni rivojlantirishda mozaika usulidan "Ilk va maktabgachayoshdagi bolalalr rivojlanishiga qo'yiladigan davlat talablari" asosida asosida ishlash aytib o'tiladi.

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